

A CONTRASTIVE ANALYSIS OF CHARACTER PSYCHOLOGY IN THE SHORT STORIES OF SOMERSET MAUGHAM AND ABDULLA KAHHOR

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Abstract: *This study examines the artistic interpretation of character psychology in the short stories of Somerset Maugham and Abdulla Kahhor through the comparative-contrastive method. The research analyzes the characters' inner experiences, psychological conflicts, and psychological states shaped by the social environment, identifying their common and distinctive features. In particular, the development of character psychology is comparatively explored through Maugham's "The Verger" and Kahhor's "The Extinguished Volcano." The findings reveal that adaptability and practical thinking are dominant in Maugham's story, whereas internal conflict and psychological decline caused by the loss of social status play a leading role in Kahhor's story.*

Keywords: *Character psychology, contrastive-comparative method, inner conflict, psychological crisis, character dynamics, social environment.*

Аннотация: *В данном исследовании художественная интерпретация психологии персонажа в рассказах Сомерсета Моэма и Абдуллы Каххора рассматривается на основе сравнительно-сопоставительного метода. В работе анализируются внутренние переживания героев, психологические конфликты и психологические состояния, формирующиеся под влиянием социальной среды, а также выявляются их общие и отличительные особенности. В частности, направления развития психологии героя сравнительно анализируются на примере рассказов Сомерсета Моэма «Священник» и Абдуллы Каххора «Потухший вулкан». В результате исследования научно обосновывается, что в рассказе Моэма доминируют адаптивность и практическое мышление, тогда как в рассказе Каххора ведущую роль играют внутренний конфликт и психологический упадок, связанный с утратой социального статуса.*

Ключевые слова: *Психология персонажа, сравнительно-сопоставительный метод, внутренний конфликт, психологический кризис, динамика характера, социальная среда.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu tadqiqotda Somerset Moem va Abdulla Qahhor hikoyalarida qahramon psixologiyasining badiiy talqini qiyosiy-chog'ishtirish metodi asosida o'rganiladi. Ilmiy izlanish davomida qahramonlarning ichki kechinmalari, ruhiy ziddiyatlari va ijtimoiy muhit ta'sirida shakllanuvchi psixologik holatlari tahlil qilinib, ularning mushtarak hamda o'ziga xos jihatlari aniqlanadi. Xususan, Moemning "Ruhoniy" va Qahhorning "So'ngan vulqon" hikoyalari misolida qahramon psixologiyasining rivojlanish yo'nalishlari qiyosiy yoritiladi. Tahlil natijasida Moem hikoyasida moslashuvchanlik va amaliy tafakkur ustuvorligi, Qahhor hikoyasida esa ichki ziddiyat va ijtimoiy mavqe yo'qotish bilan bog'liq ruhiy tanazzul yetakchi o'rin egallashi ilmiy asoslanadi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: Qahramon psixologiyasi, qiyosiy-chog‘ishtirish metodi, ichki konflikt, ruhiy inqiroz, xarakter dinamikasi, ijtimoiy muhit.

The study of character psychology plays an important role in understanding the inner essence of a literary work. In realistic literature, human emotions, inner experiences, and the relationship between an individual and society are depicted deeply and truthfully. Through character psychology, writers reveal the complex nature of human beings by portraying their speech, behavior, decisions, and psychological reactions. In realistic works, character psychology not only reflects reality but also reveals the factors that shape human character, including the social environment, historical conditions, and personal experience. As a result, social problems and moral conflicts are artistically expressed through the characters' inner experiences.

In modern literary studies, the comparative analysis of character psychology is of great scholarly importance. Comparing the representation of human psychology in different national literatures helps identify their common and distinctive features. In this regard, the comparative-contrastive method serves as an effective approach for revealing especially differences in comparative literature.[1] While analyzing the distinct features of the characters, it shows the similarities of them as well. In this regard, the short stories of Somerset Maugham and Abdulla Kahhor provide important material for the comparative study of character psychology. In the works of both writers, the complexity of human psychology is revealed through ordinary life situations, while characters' inner experiences become central to artistic expression. However, the writers use different poetic devices: Maugham emphasizes subtle irony and life paradoxes, whereas Kahhor portrays social conflicts through satire and sarcasm. This study analyzes the psychological states, inner conflicts, and reactions of characters in Maugham's "The Verger" and Kahhor's "The Extinguished Volcano." These stories reveal different models of character psychology, such as adaptability and internal contradiction. The aim of the research is to examine the artistic interpretation of character psychology in the works of both writers through the comparative-contrastive method and to identify their similarities and distinctive features.

In the short stories of Somerset Maugham and Abdulla Kahhor, character psychology serves as an important artistic means of revealing the inner experiences connected with changes in social status. In both writers' works, the psychological state of the characters is expressed through life situations, behavior, and speech. The loss of a job becomes a turning point that deeply exposes their inner world. However, this process develops differently: in one case, dismissal leads to adaptability and inner stability, while in the other it causes internal conflict and psychological decline. In Maugham's "The Verger," the character of Albert Edward Foreman represents a model of calm inner stability and practical adaptability. After his illiteracy is revealed, he is unexpectedly dismissed from his position, which becomes a major turning point in his life. Although he tries to remain calm outwardly, his inner suffering is evident, as "his lips trembled involuntarily with humiliation." [2] Walking through the streets after leaving the church, Foreman feels confused and uncertain about his future. At the same time, he realizes that he no longer wants to return to serving others, which reflects his growing sense of independence and psychological transformation. The character's inner thoughts take a new direction while he is wandering through the streets. A simple desire to buy a cigarette leads him to an important observation: there is no tobacco shop on the long street. This ordinary fact inspires a new idea, and he realizes that opening a tobacco shop there could be profitable. At that moment, the

character overcomes his psychological crisis and turns toward active change in life. Foreman's later success clearly demonstrates his psychological development. Starting with a small shop, he gradually becomes the owner of several stores. His practical thinking, determination, and inner confidence play a key role in this process. His success is connected not with chance, but with his inner stability and ability to evaluate situations wisely.

In Abdulla Kahhor's "The Extinguished Volcano," the character of Brother Shermat represents a completely different model of human psychology - inner conflict and psychological decline caused by the loss of social status. Having spent many years in leadership positions, Brother Shermat is portrayed as a man deeply attached to authority and respect. However, his gradual demotion leaves a deep impact on his inner world and becomes the starting point of his psychological crisis. From the beginning of the story, the character's emotional instability is noticeable. Although he usually enjoys eating, "Brother Shermat could not eat the pilaf that day," which reveals his inner anxiety and emotional pressure. Even though he understands the situation, he cannot accept it and tries to justify himself by saying that he has always been "a soldier of the government." This shows that he measures his value only through his past status and achievements. A turning point in Brother Shermat's psychology comes when he is called an "extinguished volcano." This expression becomes a painful blow to his inner world, symbolizing the end of his social importance and declining inner strength. From that moment, his psychological conflict deepens, and feelings of humiliation and dissatisfaction begin to dominate his inner life. At the end of the story, the character's psychology is revealed ironically. When the bank manager asks what he might have become if he had been educated, Foreman calmly replies that he would probably still have been a verger at St. Peter's Church. This response reflects his inner freedom, life experience, and ability to look at his past with irony. Through Foreman's character, Somerset Maugham creates a model of adaptable, active, and psychologically stable personality. When Brother Shermat arrives at his new, lower position, his psychological crisis becomes even more visible. Seeing the small and modest office, "his eyelids reddened and his throat tightened," revealing his wounded pride and inner suffering. Although he tries to appear calm and delivers a formal speech, his words reflect an artificial attempt to hide his emotional pain rather than genuine confidence. The deepest expression of the character's psychology appears in the scene where he walks along the street trying to encourage himself. He tells himself to "walk proudly so that people think he owns a car and is simply walking for pleasure." [3] This shows his attempt to cover his inner emptiness with outward dignity. However, reality destroys this illusion when drivers insult him, increasing his psychological pressure. Finally, he sadly admits that he has now reached the point of being insulted even by drivers, which marks the final stage of his inner decline. Through the character of Brother Shermat, Abdulla Kahhor creates a tragic and conflict-driven model of character psychology. Unable to adapt to new conditions, the hero remains attached to his past and gradually loses his inner balance. As a result, his psychological state is compared to an "extinguished volcano," symbolizing his fading inner strength and spiritual decline.

In these stories, changes in social status play a key role in revealing the characters' inner worlds. After losing his job, Foreman briefly experiences emotional uncertainty but quickly adapts to the situation, finds a new path, and maintains his inner stability. Brother Shermat, however, cannot accept his decline in status and tries to preserve his former authority, which deepens his psychological conflict. Thus, the same life situation leads to different psychological outcomes: in one case, it encourages adaptability and personal growth, while in the other, it

results in inner instability and spiritual decline. The analysis demonstrates that character psychology reflects not only individual emotions but also broader social realities. In “The Verger” and “The Extinguished Volcano,” the characters’ psychological development depends on how they respond to social change. Somerset Maugham portrays a character who turns life difficulties into new opportunities through practical thinking and inner confidence. In contrast, Abdulla Kahhor depicts a character who remains attached to his past and gradually loses his psychological balance. Overall, the constrictive analysis reveals two artistic models of character psychology: one based on adaptability and development, and the other on internal conflict and decline.

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